

Estimating Business Flood Damage Functions from Insurance Payouts: Evidence from Danish Storm Surges

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Abstract

This paper estimates a firm-level flood damage function for the insured material losses of businesses. We use administrative storm-surge compensation records from the Danish Natural Damage Council (*Naturskaderådet*) for 2011–2024, matched to building and terrain data. We first review the evidence on how flooding affects firms. We then develop a theoretical framework that decomposes total firm loss into distinct but interrelated components: production disruption, capital damage, inventory and input losses, recovery duration, and reputational effects. Guided by this framework, we estimate cross-sectional models for the intensive margin of compensated losses, comparing a log-linear OLS specification with a Gamma GLM with log link. Gross material losses rise with the physical scale of the premises, but less than proportionally, with an elasticity of 0.13–0.19. Losses are higher at lower-lying locations and vary strongly across storm-surge events. Differences across sectors point to larger losses for capital- and inventory-intensive firms, but are not robust to a joint test. We argue that insurance payouts capture only the insured physical component of flood damage. They form a lower bound on the total economic burden, which also includes business interruption and persistent output effects that the payout data omit. The results provide an empirical basis for business flood-damage functions. They also clarify how such estimates should, and should not, be used in climate adaptation appraisal.

Keywords: flood damage; storm surge; firm-level losses; damage functions; insurance payouts; climate adaptation; natural disaster economics; Denmark

JEL codes: Q54; Q51; D22; G22; R11

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1 Introduction

Climate change is expected to increase the frequency and intensity of extreme precipitation and coastal storm events across Northern Europe, heightening the risk of both riverine and coastal flooding. In Denmark, recent storm surges and sea-level rise projections indicate that flood hazards will become more frequent and severe, particularly in low-lying coastal and urban areas (Bevacqua et al., 2019). As these events intensify, they pose significant challenges for economic resilience, urban planning, and private-sector adaptation.

While the physical mechanisms of flooding are well understood, the economic implications for firms remain incompletely quantified, particularly at the firm level and for direct material damage in the business sector. Floods disrupt production, damage capital, and destroy inventories, potentially leading to long recovery times and persistent output losses. For policymakers, municipalities, and insurers, a central challenge lies in designing adaptation strategies that are both efficient and economically justified. This requires precise and empirically grounded damage-cost functions that also capture how flood impacts vary across business sectors and firm characteristics.

Existing damage assessment models tend to focus on residential or public infrastructure losses, with comparatively limited attention to the business sector from a strictly empirical point of view (Goyal and Mukherjee, 2025). Yet firms play a critical role in regional economies, not only as direct victims of flooding but also as transmitters of indirect losses through supply chains, employment, and market linkages (Prim et al., 2016; Altay and Ramirez, 2010; Yang et al., 2022). A deeper understanding of firm-level losses is therefore essential for improving climate adaptation planning and economic risk management.

This paper contributes to the literature in three ways. First, it reviews existing evidence on the economic costs of flooding for firms, with particular attention to production disruption, capital damage, inventory losses, recovery dynamics, and market effects. Second, it develops a theoretical framework that links these loss components to firm behaviour under flood risk and clarifies how direct physical damages relate to broader economic losses. Third, using ad-

ministrative insurance payouts from the Danish *Naturskaderådet* for the period 2011–2024, combined with firm and sector information, it estimates empirical damage-cost relationships for businesses affected by floods. The empirical analysis focuses on direct physical damage to commercial buildings and movable business assets, including inventory, machinery, and equipment.

The empirical results show that compensated material losses scale with the physical size of the premises but less than proportionally, are higher at lower-lying locations, and vary strongly across storm-surge events. Differences across sectors point to larger losses for capital- and inventory-intensive firms but are not robust to a joint test. We further show that insurance payouts identify only the insured physical component of flood damage and form a lower bound on the total economic burden, which also includes business interruption and persistent output effects that the payout data do not observe. Together, these findings provide a more precise empirical basis for assessing flood damage in the business sector, identify which loss components fall outside insurance-based estimates, and yield evidence-based inputs for the cost–benefit analyses and decision-support tools that guide climate adaptation investment.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 reviews the literature on firm-level flood impacts, with emphasis on production disruption, capital and inventory losses, recovery dynamics, and reputational effects. Section 3 develops a theoretical framework for firm behaviour under flood risk and decomposes total economic losses into distinct but interrelated components. Section 4 outlines the empirical strategy. Section 5 sets out the model specification and identification. Section 6 describes the administrative and registry-based data sources underpinning the analysis. Section 7 presents the estimation results, and Section 8 discusses their interpretation, policy implications, and directions for future research.

2 Literature Review

Understanding how flooding affects firms requires a synthesis of insights from environmental economics, disaster risk analysis, and production theory. In this paper we recognize that firm-level flood losses are multidimensional, encompassing both immediate physical destruction and subsequent disruptions to business operations and market relationships. Building on this perspective, the expected loss function introduced in Equation (7) decomposes total economic losses into five distinct but interrelated components: direct production disruption, capital damage, inventory and input losses, business recovery duration, and market and reputational effects. Each of these dimensions has been examined—implicitly or explicitly—in separate strands of the literature. The following subsections review the main findings and conceptual approaches associated with each loss component, highlighting how prior studies inform the modeling of firm-level flood losses in the present framework.

2.1 Literature on Business Disruption Due to Flooding

Flooding events are consistently shown to cause substantial short- and medium-term disruptions to business activity across sectors and scales (Hu et al., 2019). Empirical studies link these production interruptions to several mechanisms: labor unavailability, input inaccessibility, infrastructure damage, and breakdowns in transport and supply networks (Tanoue et al., 2020; Welch et al., 2022; Khalid and Ali, 2018; Mendoza-Tinoco et al., 2020). The magnitude and persistence of disruption vary widely depending on sectoral composition and regional adaptive capacity (Sun et al., 2022; Xia et al., 2019; Mendoza-Tinoco et al., 2020; Panwar and Sen, 2019).

Firm- and sector-level evidence demonstrates that production disruptions can be severe. Hu et al. (2019) estimate that major floods in China caused an 28% annual reduction in manufacturing output for individual firms and a 12% decline in total industrial production. Similarly, at the firm scale, Xia et al. (2019) document a 10% short-term loss in gross value added for IT and business services during the 2015 York flood. Empirical evidence shows that flooding induces substantial short-term disruptions to business activity. Using post-disaster survey data from the Netherlands, Endendijk et al. (2024) estimate that each day of flood-induced interruption reduces firms' annual revenues by approximately 0.5%, highlighting the immediate sensitivity of production processes to even brief shutdowns. Sectoral analyses from Australia further demonstrate that these effects are heterogeneous across industries: Ulubaşoğlu et al. (2018) find that the retail trade sector experiences a statistically significant lagged output decline of around 2% following flood events, largely attributable to damaged facilities and reduced local demand. Similarly, arts and recreation services exhibit comparable reductions, reflecting the vulnerability of service-oriented activities to urban flooding and mobility restrictions.

Firm size and structure also shape vulnerability. Based on a survey of 415 small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in northern England, Sakai and Yao (2023) show that smaller firms suffer disproportionately larger losses and slower recoveries, underscoring the importance of financial resilience and adaptive capacity in mitigating disruption. At a macroeconomic scale, simulation results by Li et al. (2018) for an extreme storm-flood scenario in Shanghai indicate direct production capacity losses of USD 24 billion — exceeding measured asset damages—thereby confirming that flow disruptions to output can surpass the value of physical destruction alone.

Together, these studies provide consistent evidence that flooding affects firms' temporary inoperability of production systems, which represents the reduction in effective productive capacity due to operational shutdowns and access disruptions.

2.2 Literature on Capital Loss due to Flooding

Capital loss for firms, denotes the total or partial destruction of productive physical assets that occurs during and immediately after a flood event. These assets

typically include commercial buildings, machinery, production equipment, e.g., and Information & computer technology used in the production process (Tanoue et al., 2020; Paprotny et al., 2020; Sugathan et al., 2025). Empirical evidence consistently indicates that capital losses represent a large component of total direct economic damage in flood events. For example, the 2011 Thailand flood caused estimated economic losses of approximately 22 billion USD (2005 prices), accounting for 60% of total direct damages (Tanoue et al., 2020). Similar findings for Europe show that commercial entities experience average capital losses two to three times greater than those of private households (Paprotny et al., 2020).

At the firm level, floods can cause persistent deterioration of balance-sheet capital. Sugathan et al. (2025) find that flood-affected firms in India experienced an average annual decline of 46% in total assets during the post-flood period, with substantial variation across industries. Manufacturing, utilities, and information and communication sectors exhibit the largest proportional declines in productive assets, reflecting both physical exposure and high capital specificity. By contrast, the financial and insurance sectors may exhibit temporary increases in capital values, primarily due to the expansion of loan portfolios supporting post-flood reconstruction (Sugathan et al., 2025).

Overall, this literature underscores that flood-induced capital destruction is a driver of economic loss. It underlines the need to explicitly represent capital depreciation and replacement dynamics within models of firm-level flood loss.

2.3 Literature on inventory loss due to flooding

Flood-related costs for businesses prominently include the direct physical destruction of inventory, encompassing raw materials, semi-finished goods, and finished products (Hu et al., 2019). This form of asset damage is consistently classified as a direct tangible loss in flood impact assessments (Li et al., 2018; Koks et al., 2019). The financial magnitude of such losses can be substantial: under an extreme storm-flood scenario for the Shanghai manufacturing sector, inventory damage alone was projected at approximately USD 9 billion (Li et al., 2018). Inventory is particularly susceptible to inundation, often exhibiting higher damage ratios than fixed capital at shallow flood depths, especially within the 0–1.5 m range (Li et al., 2018).

Sectoral heterogeneity in vulnerability is pronounced. High-technology and chemical manufacturing sectors exhibit the greatest exposure, with modeled inventory damage ratios approaching 0.8 at 1.5 m of floodwater (Li et al., 2018). These findings underscore the need to distinguish inventory losses from broader capital damages when estimating firm-level flood impacts. Methodological advances reflect this recognition: recent flood-damage modelling frameworks explicitly incorporate separate modules for “goods and stock” (GNS), capturing the specific exposure and fragility of stored materials and products (Schoppa et al., 2020).

Empirical analyses also highlight that inventory losses are shaped by multiple interacting factors beyond inundation depth. Firm characteristics such as

sectoral activity, asset structure, and the implementation of precautionary measures — such as elevated storage or flood barriers — explain a large share of observed variance in goods and stock damages, often surpassing the predictive power of hydrological intensity alone (Schoppa et al., 2020).

In summary, the literature identifies inventory losses as a highly variable component of direct physical damage from flooding. The loss is conditioned by sectoral composition, storage practices, and local flood dynamics.

2.4 Literature on business recovery as a result of flooding

While physical asset destruction occurs immediately during flooding, its economic repercussions often extend over several years. Recovery processes are typically slowed by elevated reconstruction costs, delayed capital replacement, and protracted operational disruptions (Tanoue et al., 2020). Empirical evidence demonstrates that these post-disaster dynamics can significantly constrain productive capacity and long-term output. For example, the 2011 Thailand flood was projected to reduce national GDP by more than 0.5% annually until 2030 due to persistent capital impairment and sluggish recovery (Tanoue et al., 2020). At the macro scale, Hu et al. (2019) identifies lagged industrial output losses of approximately 2.3% following major flood events in China, highlighting the temporal persistence of business interruption effects.

Beyond direct production stoppages, indirect and ripple effects through supply chains amplify recovery challenges. Mendoza-Tinoco et al. (2020) estimate that indirect flood losses across European industries reached 186% of direct damages, while Khalid and Ali (2018) and Yaseen et al. (2020) show that inoperability of key infrastructure in Pakistan led to system-wide productivity declines across interdependent sectors. Manufacturing and service industries dependent on just-in-time logistics or ICT infrastructure appear particularly vulnerable to extended downtime.

Overall, the literature emphasizes that business recovery after flooding is neither immediate nor uniform. Long-duration floods and high intersectoral connectivity are consistently associated with multi-year recovery horizons, underlining the importance of explicitly modeling recovery duration as a distinct component of firm-level flood losses.

2.5 Literature on business reputation effects due to flooding

Beyond the physical and operational impacts, flood-related disruptions can have reputational consequences for affected firms. Reputation embodies stakeholders' perceptions of a company's reliability, integrity, and competence, and its erosion can translate directly into financial losses (Azadegan et al., 2020). Empirical studies on supply chain disruptions demonstrate that the public announcement of major operational failures is associated with abnormal declines in shareholder value - on average 10% - reflecting the market's punitive response to perceived managerial or systemic weaknesses (Hendricks and Singhal, 2008). Such events

often lead investors to reassess the firm’s risk profile and future performance potential, effectively imposing a reputational discount on the firm’s valuation.

Reputational recovery depends heavily on a firm’s ability to contain stakeholder uncertainty. Azadegan et al. (2020) show that proactive crisis communication strategies can substantially mitigate reputational losses. Firms that demonstrate rapid, transparent, and well-coordinated responses are better able to preserve customer trust and maintain market credibility. Similarly, effective supply chain disruption management enhances perceived reliability and responsiveness, indirectly strengthening corporate reputation through sustained customer satisfaction (Saribanon et al., 2024).

Within the context of flooding, reputational effects extend beyond financial markets and directly affect customer behaviour — particularly for small businesses and retail firms that depend on local or visitor spending. Studies by Green et al. (2008) and Wedawatta et al. (2013) document that visible flood damage and negative media coverage can deter customers and tourists, causing prolonged demand shortfalls - even among unflooded firms in otherwise flooded area. These reputational externalities underscore that flood-induced reputational losses are not confined to directly damaged firms but can cascade across entire local economies.

Overall, the literature suggests that reputational impacts represent a distinct and often enduring driver of economic loss.

3 Theoretical Framework

3.1 Profit Maximization under Flood Risk

Firms are assumed to operate as profit-maximizing entities facing production uncertainty arising from environmental shocks. In the absence of flooding, the profit of firm i can be represented as:

$$\pi_i = p_i q_i(L_i, M_i, K_i) - w_i L_i - c_{M,i} M_i - r_i K_i \tag{1}$$

where $q_i(\cdot)$ is a neoclassical production function that depends on labor L_i , intermediate material inputs M_i , and physical capital K_i ; p_i is the output price; w_i is the wage rate; $c_{M,i}$ the unit cost of materials; and r_i the user cost of capital. The firm chooses input quantities to maximize expected profit:

$$\max_{L_i, M_i, K_i} E[\pi_i] = E[p_i q_i(L_i, M_i, K_i)] - w_i L_i - c_{M,i} M_i - r_i K_i \tag{2}$$

subject to technological and budget constraints.

When flooding occurs, firms face a reduction in productive capacity and potential destruction of inputs and assets. Let F denote the occurrence of a flood characterized by intensity ϕ and duration T_F . The production function under flood conditions can be written as:

$$q_i^F = (1 - \theta_{q,i}(\phi, T_F)) q_i ((1 - \theta_{L,i})L_i, (1 - \theta_{M,i})M_i, (1 - \theta_{K,i})K_i) \quad (3)$$

where the parameters $\theta_{L,i}$, $\theta_{M,i}$, and $\theta_{K,i}$ represent the proportions of labor, materials, and capital rendered unavailable or damaged due to flooding, and $\theta_{q,i}(\phi, T_F)$ captures additional operational inefficiencies not directly attributable to input loss (e.g., transportation barriers, safety restrictions, information and communication technology disruptions, or power outages).

The realized profit under flooding is thus:

$$\pi_i^F = p_i q_i^F - w_i L_i - c_{M,i} M_i - r_i K_i - C_{R,i} \quad (4)$$

where $C_{R,i}$ denotes recovery and clean-up costs incurred after the event. Even during periods of halted production, some costs such as wages or capital expenses may remain fixed, implying a discontinuous adjustment process in the short run.

3.2 Components of Flood-Related Losses

Total firm losses from flooding, $\mathcal{L}_{F,i}$, can be decomposed into distinct but interrelated components reflecting different economic mechanisms:

(a) Direct production disruption (flow loss): Flooding may cause temporary shutdowns, reducing operational output. This can be formalized as a shock to productive capacity, as a result of both direct input unavailability and broader operational inefficiencies. We can combine these effects into a single composite production disruption shock, Θ_i , defined as a function of its underlying components:

$$\Theta_i = g(\theta_{q,i}, \theta_{L,i}, \theta_{M,i}, \theta_{K,i}) \quad (5)$$

This composite shock, Θ_i , represents the total immediate impact on the firm's productive capacity. For labor-intensive sectors, even minor access disruptions may result in a complete halt of production or service delivery.

(b) Capital damage (stock loss): Physical assets such as machinery, buildings, or information and communication technology infrastructure may suffer damage, reducing their effective productive capacity to $K_i' = (1 - \delta_{F,i})K_i$. The depreciation rate $\delta_{F,i}$ represents the proportion of capital value lost due to the event and determines the long-term financial burden of replacement or repair.

(c) Inventory and input losses: Firms holding inventories face potential permanent destruction of stored stock, distinct from the temporary unavailability or damage to inputs allocated for current production (captured in $\theta_{M,i}$ under production disruption). The permanent loss of inventory can be expressed as $\mathcal{L}_{I,i} = p_{I,i} \Delta I_i$, where ΔI_i is the quantity of inventory destroyed and $p_{I,i}$ its per-unit value. This loss is particularly relevant for retail and storage-intensive

sectors. Note that the inventory loss is different than the disruption of the flow of material

(d) Business interruption and recovery costs: Even after physical inundation subsides, firms incur revenue losses during the recovery phase due to ongoing downtime, insurance processing, and facility restoration. This can be expressed as the foregone profit stream over the recovery period T_R :

$$\mathcal{L}_{T,i} = \int_0^{T_R} [p_i q_i(L_i, M_i, K_i) - w_i L_i - c_{M,i} M_i] dt \quad (6)$$

Note that capital costs ($r_i K_i$) are excluded from this integral, as they are treated as fixed and sunk expenses that continue to accrue during the short-term recovery period, irrespective of whether production is halted or resumed.

(e) Market and reputational effects: Flood-induced closures may cause temporary or permanent loss of clientele, reducing expected future revenues. This can be captured through a reputational discount factor $\rho_i \in [0, 1]$ applied to post-flood profits, such that $E[\pi_i^{post}] = \rho_i E[\pi_i]$.

3.3 Sectoral Heterogeneity in Loss Mechanisms

We hypothesize that the relative importance of these loss components varies across sectors due to differences in production structure, capital intensity, and substitutability of inputs.

Table 1: Sectoral heterogeneity in flood-related loss mechanisms.

Sector	Main Exposure Channel	Main Loss Components	Expected Economic Implication
Service and Retail	Labor and customer access	(a), (c), (e)	Highly sensitive to temporary disruptions; rapid but costly recovery; limited physical capital exposure.
Office-based Firms	Infrastructure (information and communication technology, transport)	(a), (d), (e)	Moderate exposure; remote work offers partial mitigation; losses depend on data security and connectivity.
Storage and Production	Capital and physical assets	(a), (b), (c), (d)	High capital specificity amplifies damage costs; long recovery times and strong dependence on local infrastructure.

This hypothesized heterogeneity highlights the relevance to account for sector-specific production structures and capacities when evaluating the economic consequences of flood events.

3.4 Conceptual Loss Function

Combining the above components, total expected flood-related losses can be expressed as a function of hazard characteristics, exposure, and sectoral sensitivity:

$$E[\mathcal{L}_{F,i}] = f(\Theta_i, \delta_{F,i}, \Delta I_i, T_{R,i}, \rho_i) \quad (7)$$

where:

- Θ_i : **Direct production disruption.** Represents the proportional reduction in effective output due to temporary shutdowns, input inaccessibility, or reduced labor availability during flooding (component (a)). It captures the short-run loss of productive capacity.
- $\delta_{F,i}$: **Capital damage (stock loss).** Denotes the proportion of physical and productive capital (buildings, machinery, ICT) destroyed or rendered unusable by flooding (component (b)). This parameter determines the long-term depreciation of the firm’s capital stock.
- ΔI_i : **Inventory and input losses.** Measures the value of stored goods, raw materials, and intermediate inputs permanently damaged or destroyed during the flood (component (c)). Particularly relevant for retail, warehousing, and manufacturing sectors.
- $T_{R,i}$: **Business interruption and recovery duration.** Represents the period required for the firm to resume normal operations after flooding (component (d)). Longer recovery times increase foregone revenue and production losses beyond the immediate event.
- ρ_i : **Market and reputational effects.** A discount factor on post-flood profitability capturing reduced customer demand, disrupted supply relationships, or reputational damage (component (e)). Lower ρ_i values indicate larger persistent losses.

Together, these parameters provide a conceptual bridge between the firm’s profit-maximization framework and the empirical loss distribution. They encapsulate both direct physical impacts and indirect economic consequences, allowing for sector-specific identification of vulnerability and recovery dynamics.

This framework provides a theoretical foundation for quantifying firm-level losses from coastal flooding and for assessing adaptation measures that can mitigate the expected loss components.

4 Empirical Strategy

4.1 Overview

We use cross-sectional business-location claim data covering Danish storm-surge events during 2011–2024. The claims data come from the Danish *Naturskaderådet*

and record compensation for direct physical damage to commercial properties and business assets. The empirical analysis focuses on the intensive margin of losses: conditional on a positive compensated claim, we estimate how gross material losses vary with building characteristics, location, event conditions, and company type.

4.2 Capital Damage and Inventory Loss in the Payout Data

The theoretical framework distinguishes between two central components of direct physical loss: capital damage and inventory or input losses. Capital damage includes damage to buildings, machinery, equipment, ICT infrastructure, and other productive assets. Inventory and input losses include destroyed raw materials, intermediate goods, finished goods, and other movable business contents. This distinction is substantively important because the relative importance of these loss components is likely to differ across sectors. For example, industry, storage, and transport firms may be more exposed through fixed capital and machinery, while service, retail, and hospitality firms may be more exposed through inventories, equipment, and customer-facing premises.

The insurance data do not provide a complete asset-level decomposition of each claim. Instead, we observe the compensated payout associated with a business-location claim. This payout may combine damage to buildings, movable productive assets, inventories, and eligible clean-up or building-service costs. We therefore interpret the deductible-corrected payout as an aggregate measure of insured direct material loss, while using company group, building characteristics, and location variables to study how the level of loss varies across firms with different likely asset compositions.

Let $\widehat{L}_i^{\text{payout}}$ denote the observed net insurance payout for claim i . Conceptually, this payout can be written as

$$\widehat{L}_i^{\text{payout}} \approx L_i^{(b)} + L_i^{(c)} + L_i^{(\text{bs})}, \quad (8)$$

where $L_i^{(b)}$ denotes capital damage, $L_i^{(c)}$ denotes inventory and input losses, $L_i^{(\text{bs})}$ denotes covered building-service and clean-up costs. The model does not separately identify $L_i^{(b)}$ and $L_i^{(c)}$ for each claim. Instead, it estimates how total gross material loss varies with observable proxies for exposure and vulnerability. Sectoral differences are interpreted as reduced-form evidence of heterogeneity in the composition and scale of exposed assets, rather than as a direct accounting decomposition of capital and inventory damages.

5 Model specification and identification

We estimate parsimonious cross-sectional damage models for the intensive margin of business storm-surge losses. The unit of observation is a matched business-location–event claim with a positive deductible-corrected and inflation-adjusted

payout. The models therefore describe variation in compensated gross losses conditional on a paid claim.

Let L_i denote gross material loss for claim i , measured in 2023 DKK. We estimate two specifications with a common set of regressors. First, we estimate a log-linear OLS model,

$$\log(L_i) = \alpha + X_i' \beta + \gamma_{g(i)} + \delta_{e(i)} + \lambda_{z(i)} + \varepsilon_i, \quad (9)$$

where the vector X_i contains the continuous and binary explanatory variables: log unit size, terrain elevation, an indicator for a registered basement, an indicator for unknown basement status, and an indicator for whether the address is located within 50 metres of a harbour. The terms $\gamma_{g(i)}$, $\delta_{e(i)}$, and $\lambda_{z(i)}$ denote company-group, event-group, and coastal-zone fixed effects, respectively. Service/retail/hospitality firms and smaller events serve as the reference categories.

Second, we estimate a Gamma GLM with log link and the same right-hand side, because losses are positive and strongly right-skewed,

$$\begin{aligned} L_i \mid X_i, g(i), e(i), z(i) &\sim \text{Gamma}(\mu_i, \kappa), \\ \log(\mu_i) &= \alpha + X_i' \beta + \gamma_{g(i)} + \delta_{e(i)} + \lambda_{z(i)}. \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

The OLS specification estimates semi-elasticities in log losses, while the Gamma-log model estimates multiplicative effects on the conditional mean of losses in levels. Reporting both specifications provides a check on whether the estimated damage gradients are sensitive to modelling log losses or loss levels directly.

Identification comes from within-sample variation across compensated business locations after conditioning on event group and coastal zone. The coefficients are interpreted as conditional damage gradients rather than causal effects in a strict experimental sense. Company-group coefficients may capture sectoral differences in asset composition, inventories, insurance coverage, and unobserved production technology. Event-group effects absorb common differences in storm characteristics and claims conditions across events, while coastal-zone fixed effects control for broad spatial differences in exposure and coastal morphology. Standard errors are HC1 robust and clustered by municipality. We report joint Wald tests for the company-group and event-group indicators.

6 Data

6.1 Overview

The empirical analysis combines property-level storm-surge compensation records from the Danish Natural Damage Council (*Naturskaderådet*) with building information from the Danish Building and Dwelling Register (BBR). The claims data are linked to geospatial information on terrain elevation and flood exposure, allowing each compensated business claim to be described by both the physical characteristics of the affected property and its local hazard conditions.

The unit of observation is a business claim for which storm-surge damage was assessed and compensation was awarded. The main outcome variable is the monetary compensation paid for the reported damage. Thus, the analysis describes observed insured losses conditional on a successful compensation claim, rather than the full population of firms exposed to flooding.

6.2 Insurance claims and the payout measure

Compensation records were obtained from the Danish Natural Damage Council (*Naturskaderådet*, formerly *Stormrådet*), which administers Denmark’s statutory compensation scheme for storm-surge damage. Under this scheme, all properties covered by fire insurance are automatically insured against eligible storm-surge losses. Following an officially declared storm-surge event, reported damages are assessed and compensated according to the provisions of the scheme (Naturskaderådet, 2025).

The unit of analysis is a business-location claim with a positive compensation payment. Insurance claims may cover damage to building structures, movable productive assets, inventories, and eligible clean-up costs. In some cases, building damage and business contents are registered as separate claim records, reflecting differences in insurance coverage or ownership. We therefore aggregate claims registered at the same address within the same storm-surge event to obtain a single compensation measure for each affected business location.

The primary outcome variable is the positive compensation payment awarded for reported storm-surge damage to business locations. Insurance claims may cover direct material losses to building structures, productive capital and equipment, inventories, and eligible clean-up costs. In some cases, damages to buildings and business contents are registered as separate claim records, reflecting differences in insurance coverage or ownership. We therefore aggregate claims registered at the same address within the same storm-surge event to obtain a single compensation measure for each affected business location.

Reported payouts for business claims are net of the statutory deductible, which corresponds to 14% of the assessed loss subject to a minimum deductible of 14,000 DKK (Naturskaderådet, 2025). Claims with zero payouts are excluded from the estimation sample, as these primarily represent rejected claims or damages below the deductible threshold. To recover an estimate of gross material damage before the deductible, we add back the implied self-payment. Let $P_i \equiv \widehat{L}_i^{\text{payout}}$ denote the positive net payout for claim i . Gross material damage is then calculated as

$$\widehat{L}_i^{\text{gross}} = \begin{cases} P_i + 14,000, & \text{if } 0 < P_i \leq 86,000, \\ \frac{P_i}{1 - 0.14}, & \text{if } P_i > 86,000. \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The two branches reflect the minimum deductible binding for smaller claims and the proportional 14% deductible binding above an assessed loss of 100,000 DKK; the rule is continuous at the kink, where $P_i = 86,000$ DKK. This deductible-corrected gross loss $\widehat{L}_i^{\text{gross}}$ is the empirical outcome used throughout the analysis

and corresponds to L_i in the model equations of Section 5. Furthermore, all monetary values are expressed in constant 2023 Danish kroner (DKK), using the annual average consumer price index reported by Statistics Denmark, Table PRIS8.

We identify the storm-surge event sample directly from the event names recorded in the *Naturskaderådet* claims data. The sample includes the main Danish storm-surge events observed during 2013–2023: Bodil, Egon, Gorm, Urd, the January 2017 Baltic Sea surge, Alfrida, Ingolf, Malik, the October 2023 Baltic Sea surge, and Pia (Table 2).¹ The analysis is restricted to claims associated with commercial properties (*Erhverv*), excluding residential dwellings and holiday homes from the estimation sample.

Table 2 reports the number of commercial claim records associated with each storm-surge event in the source data. These counts describe the distribution of claims across events and should not be interpreted as the number of paid compensation observations used in the econometric analysis. The estimation sample is based on positive payouts after excluding zero-payment claims and, where relevant, aggregating separate claim records at the same address and event into a single business-location payout.

Table 2: Storm-surge events identified in the business-claim data

Storm-surge event	Claim records	Event size group
Stormfloden 20.–21. oktober 2023	508	Large event
Stormfloden efter stormen Alfrida	12	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Bodil	108	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Egon	6	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Gorm	10	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Ingolf	2	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Malik 30-01-2022	3	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Pia	9	Small event
Stormfloden efter stormen Urd	3	Small event
Stormfloden fra Østersøen 4–5. januar 2017	35	Small event

Note: Claim records refer to commercial claims recorded in the *Naturskaderådet* source data by storm-surge event. These counts are descriptive and do not correspond directly to the final estimation sample, which is based on positive compensation payments and aggregates multiple claim records at the same address and event where relevant.

6.3 The building and dwelling register and temporal matching

Structural and locational building characteristics are obtained from the Danish Building and Dwelling Register (BBR). At the building and unit level, the

¹In Denmark, storms are named by the Danish Meteorological Institute, and these names provide a practical identifier for each event.

register provides information on floor area, building footprint, year of construction and renovation, exterior wall and roof materials, heating system, basement presence and basement size, as well as geographic coordinates.

A key limitation is that BBR is a continuously updated administrative register rather than a historical archive. The live register therefore reflects the current state of each property and does not directly recover building characteristics at the time of past storm-surge events. To address this, we compiled archived BBR extracts for 2011, 2015, 2016, 2018, 2020, 2022, and 2023. Each storm-surge event is matched to the nearest available register snapshot; for example, claims from the December 2013 Bodil event are linked to the 2015 extract.

The archived extracts were harmonized to a common data structure by reconciling variable names, definitions, and coverage across years. Where specific attributes were unavailable in a given extract, notably basement indicators, values were imputed from the nearest available snapshot using the unit identifier. Consequently, the building variables used in the analysis represent the closest available historical approximation to conditions at the time of the event, rather than exact contemporaneous measurements. Given the design of the BBR register, this provides the most feasible reconstruction of historical property characteristics.

6.4 Linking claims to the register

The compensation records identify affected properties by address, but do not contain the BBR unit identifier. We therefore link claims to BBR building and unit records using a staged address-matching procedure implemented within municipality and postcode. To limit the matching universe to plausibly exposed properties, candidate BBR records are restricted to locations below 5 m elevation, since direct storm-surge inundation is unlikely above this threshold.

Addresses in both datasets are first standardized to a common format. Text strings are converted to lower case, Danish characters are transliterated ($\text{\ae} \rightarrow \text{ae}$, $\text{\o} \rightarrow \text{oe}$, $\text{\aa} \rightarrow \text{aa}$), punctuation is removed, and each address is parsed into street name, house number, unit designation, postcode, and city. Claims are then matched to BBR records through a sequence of increasingly permissive criteria. The first stage requires an exact match on the full cleaned address. The second stage applies to claims without a unit designation and requires an exact match on postcode, municipality, street name, and house number. The third stage allows for minor spelling differences in street names using Jaro–Winkler string distance, retaining matches with a distance of at most 0.12, conditional on exact matches for postcode, municipality, and house number (Van der Loo, 2014). This procedure allows typographical variation in street names while preventing matches across different house numbers.

Each claim is assigned a single best BBR match and classified by match quality. Unit-level matches identify a unique BBR unit at the address. Building-level matches identify a unique building but not a unique unit within that building. Claims for which no sufficiently reliable match is found are classified

as unmatched. The main analysis uses unit-level matches where available, while building-level matches are retained for robustness checks and analyses conducted at the building level.

Across the ten storm-surge events, the matching procedure identified 696 high-confidence matches among 1,412 commercial claim records, corresponding to an overall match rate of 49% (Table 3). Match rates vary substantially across events. The October 2023 Baltic Sea surge accounts for the largest share of the matched sample, with 508 matches out of 718 claim records, corresponding to a match rate of 71%. By contrast, Bodil contains 423 commercial claim records, but only 108 high-confidence matches, yielding a match rate of 26%. For the remaining events, the number of commercial claims is relatively small, and the resulting match rates are therefore sensitive to only a few matched or unmatched records.

The non-trivial share of unmatched claims is partly structural. The compensation data identify the policyholder’s claim address, which will often correspond to the affected property, but not necessarily in all cases. In addition, business claims may involve separate records for buildings, productive assets, inventories, or clean-up costs, and these records are not always registered in a way that maps uniquely to a BBR unit or building. The purpose of the matching procedure is therefore not to maximize the number of linked observations, but to ensure that the structural, locational, and elevation attributes assigned to each claim are reliable. Ambiguous or low-confidence candidates are left unmatched, so the final linked sample deliberately favours precision over recall.

Table 3: Address matching of commercial storm-surge claim records

Storm-surge event	Claim records	Matched records	Match rate
Stormfloden efter stormen Bodil	423	108	25.5%
Stormfloden efter stormen Egon	26	6	23.1%
Stormfloden efter stormen Gorm	19	10	52.6%
Stormfloden efter stormen Urd	17	3	17.6%
Stormfloden fra Østersøen 4-5. januar 2017	118	35	29.7%
Stormfloden efter stormen Ingolf	18	2	11.1%
Stormfloden efter stormen Alfrida	43	12	27.9%
Stormfloden efter stormen Malik 30-01-2022	7	3	42.9%
Stormfloden 20.-21. oktober 2023	718	508	70.8%
Stormfloden efter stormen Pia	23	9	39.1%
Total	1,412	696	49.3%

Note: Claim records refer to commercial storm-surge claims in the *Naturskaderådet* source data. Matched records are high-confidence address matches to BBR building or unit records. The counts describe the matching procedure and do not correspond directly to the final estimation sample, which is based on positive compensation payments and aggregates multiple claim records at the same address and event where relevant.

6.5 Descriptive statistics

6.6 Continuous explanatory variables

Table 4 reports summary statistics for the continuous variables used in the analysis. The final matched sample contains 371 business-location observations. The average registered unit size is 607 m², but the distribution is strongly right-skewed, with a median of 217 m² and a maximum of 28,145 m². This reflects substantial heterogeneity in the physical scale of affected business premises, ranging from small service and retail units to large industrial or storage facilities. Elevation is generally low, consistent with the storm-surge setting. The mean elevation is 1.77 m above sea level, with an interquartile range from 1.38 to 1.97 m.

Table 4: Summary statistics for continuous variables

	Variable	N	Mean	SD	Min	P25	Median	P75	Max
unit_size	Unit size	371	607.26	1685.18	1	87.00	217.00	564.50	28145.00
elevation	Elevation	371	1.77	0.71	-0.72	1.38	1.64	1.97	4.89

6.7 Explanatory dummy variables

Table 5 summarizes the binary building and location indicators. Registered basements are relatively uncommon: only 15 observations, corresponding to 4.0% of the sample, are recorded as having a basement. However, basement status is unknown for 26.1% of observations, reflecting incomplete information in the register for this attribute. A substantial share of the sample is located close to harbor areas: 129 observations, or 34.8%, are within 50 m of a harbor location. This is consistent with the exposure profile of commercial storm-surge damages, where firms located in low-lying harbor and waterfront areas are particularly likely to be affected.

Table 5: Summary statistics for dummy variables

	Variable	N	No. = 1	Share = 1	No. = 0	Missing
basement_yes	Basement	371	15	4.0	356	0
basement_unknown	Basement unknown	371	97	26.1	274	0
harbor_location_50	Harbor location within 50 m	371	129	34.8	242	0

6.8 Category variables - fixed effect

Table 6 describes the categorical variables used to control for sectoral, event-level, and coastal-zone heterogeneity. Service, retail, and hospitality firms constitute the largest company group, accounting for 46.9% of the sample, followed by industry, storage, and transport firms at 29.6%. Office-based firms account

for 17.8%, while the residual “other” category represents 5.7%. The event distribution is highly concentrated: the October 2023 storm surge accounts for 69.8% of the observations, while Bodil accounts for 18.3%. The remaining smaller events jointly account for 11.9% of the sample. This concentration implies that event fixed effects are important for separating general vulnerability patterns from event-specific exposure and reporting conditions.

Table 6: Frequency table for categorical variables

Variable	Category	N	Share
Company group	Service/retail/hospitality	174	46.9
Company group	Office-based	66	17.8
Company group	Industry/storage/transport	110	29.6
Company group	Other	21	5.7
Event group	Smaller events	44	11.9
Event group	Bodil	68	18.3
Event group	October 2023	259	69.8
Coast zone	Lillebælt	108	29.1
Coast zone	Bornholm	6	1.6
Coast zone	Køge Bugt/S-Øresund	21	5.7
Coast zone	Limfjord	8	2.2
Coast zone	Lolland-Falster	11	3.0
Coast zone	N-Øresund/N-Sjælland	12	3.2
Coast zone	Nordjylland/Kattegat	2	0.5
Coast zone	Roskilde/Isefjord	34	9.2
Coast zone	SE-Sjælland	38	10.2
Coast zone	Storebælt/Belt	11	3.0
Coast zone	Sydfynske Øhav	43	11.6
Coast zone	Sønderjylland	63	17.0
Coast zone	Vestkyst/Vadehav	14	3.8

6.9 Dependent variable: loss estimate

The dependent variable is the estimated direct material loss associated with each compensated business-location claim. It is constructed from the inflation-adjusted insurance payout after correcting for the statutory deductible. We interpret this measure as the compensated cost of storm-surge damage to buildings, productive capital, inventories, and eligible clean-up activities. The variable therefore captures insured direct material losses, but not broader indirect costs such as production interruptions, customer losses, or longer-term recovery effects.

Table 7 reports the distribution of the loss estimate in the final estimation sample. The distribution is highly right-skewed. The median loss is 294,376 DKK, while the mean is 877,803 DKK, indicating that a relatively small number of large claims has a substantial influence on the average. The

interquartile range extends from 123,080 DKK to 670,628 DKK, while the maximum observed loss is 30.0 million DKK.

Table 7: Summary statistics for the dependent variable

Variable	Min.	P25	Median	Mean	P75	Max.
Loss estimate	22,320	123,080	294,376	877,803	670,628	30,041,869

Note: Loss estimates are deductible-corrected and inflation-adjusted to 2023 DKK. The measure captures insured direct material losses related to buildings, productive capital, inventories, and eligible clean-up costs.

Table 8 and Figure 1 describe how losses vary across company groups. Industry, storage, and transport firms have the highest mean loss, at 1.39 million DKK, compared with approximately 0.65–0.68 million DKK for service, retail, hospitality, office-based firms, and the residual category. However, the difference in means is driven partly by the upper tail of the distribution. Median losses are more similar across groups, ranging from 221,248 DKK in the residual category to 334,919 DKK among industry, storage, and transport firms.

Table 8: Loss estimates by company group

Company group	N	Mean	SD	P25	Median	P75	Max.
Service/retail/hospitality	174	652,136	2,326,770	108,051	264,464	579,285	30,041,869
Office-based	66	681,008	1,081,815	150,710	316,658	729,268	7,383,721
Industry/storage/transport	110	1,392,575	3,115,060	175,155	334,919	756,176	19,092,201
Other	21	669,685	969,723	98,959	221,248	771,820	3,887,730

Note: Values are reported in 2023 DKK. Loss estimates are based on positive compensated claims and are corrected for the statutory deductible.

Figure 1 confirms the strong skewness of the loss distribution. The boxplots show broadly overlapping interquartile ranges across company groups, but also several large outliers, particularly among service, retail, and hospitality firms and among industry, storage, and transport firms. To make the distribution readable, the figure uses a logarithmic vertical axis.

Figure 1: Distribution of loss estimates by company group

Figure 2 reports mean losses with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals. The point estimate is highest for industry, storage, and transport firms, consistent with the expectation that these firms may hold more physical capital, machinery, and inventories at exposed locations. However, the bootstrap intervals are wide and overlap across groups, reflecting both the skewed distribution and the relatively limited number of observations in some categories.

Figure 2: Mean loss estimates by company group with 95% bootstrap confidence intervals

Formal distributional tests provide no strong evidence that unadjusted losses differ systematically across company groups. A Welch ANOVA applied to the log loss value gives ($F = 1.955$), with ($p = 0.127$), while a Kruskal–Wallis test on the loss value gives ($\chi^2 = 3.938$), with ($p = 0.268$). Holm-adjusted pairwise Welch and Wilcoxon tests similarly do not reject equality between any pair of company groups at conventional significance levels. The descriptive evidence therefore suggests that industry, storage, and transport firms have higher average losses, but that this difference is not statistically distinguishable in the unadjusted distribution. We therefore choose to treat the three sector specific groupings in one model.

7 Model estimation results

Table 9 reports the estimated gross-loss models. Throughout, the OLS coefficients describe effects on log (geometric-mean) loss, while the Gamma-log coefficients describe effects on the arithmetic conditional mean of loss in levels; level effects are reported as $\exp(\beta) - 1$ percentage changes. The two columns therefore answer slightly different questions, and differences between them are informative about whether a gradient operates on typical claims or on the large claims that dominate the arithmetic mean.

Unit size is positively associated with gross material loss in both specifications. The coefficient is 0.134 in the log-linear OLS model and 0.193 in the Gamma-log model, implying that a 10 per cent larger unit is associated with approximately 1.3–1.9 % higher loss, conditional on the remaining covariates.

The elasticity is well below one: losses increase with the physical scale of the business premises, but less than proportionally.

Elevation has the expected negative sign in both models. In the OLS specification, a one-meter increase in elevation is associated with approximately 19 % lower gross loss and is statistically significant. The Gamma-log estimate is smaller, corresponding to roughly 10 % lower conditional mean loss, and is not statistically significant. This pattern is consistent with elevation mattering more for typical claims than for the largest claims that drive the arithmetic mean. The results thus provide some evidence that lower-lying business locations experience higher compensated losses, although the strength of the relationship depends on the estimator.

The basement and harbor indicators are not precisely estimated. Registered basements and unknown basement status both enter positively, but neither coefficient is statistically significant. The harbor-proximity indicator changes sign across specifications and is insignificant in both models. These variables therefore provide no robust evidence of independent damage gradients once unit size, elevation, company group, event group, and coastal-zone fixed effects are included.

The company-group coefficients suggest that industry, storage, and transport firms may experience larger losses than the service, retail, and hospitality reference group. This pattern is strongest in the Gamma-log model, where the coefficient of 0.655 implies approximately 93 per cent higher conditional mean losses. Although this contrast is individually significant in the Gamma-log model, the corresponding OLS estimate is smaller and not statistically significant, and the joint test for company groups does not reject equality across sectors ($p = 0.380$). Because the joint test is the more conservative summary, we treat the sectoral pattern as suggestive rather than conclusive.

Event effects are more pronounced. The October 2023 storm surge is associated with substantially higher losses than the smaller-event reference group in both specifications. The OLS coefficient of 1.014 corresponds to approximately 176 % higher losses, while the Gamma-log coefficient of 1.369 implies a conditional mean loss almost four times as large (a factor of 3.9). By contrast, the Bodil coefficient is positive but not statistically significant. The joint test for event groups is significant ($p = 0.015$), indicating that event-level conditions explain an important part of the observed variation in compensated business losses.

Overall, the results indicate that gross material losses are systematically related to the physical scale of the affected business location and to the storm-surge event. Elevation is negatively associated with losses, while sectoral differences are present mainly in the level-loss model. The modest explanatory power of the OLS model ($R^2 = 0.159$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.106$) is consistent with substantial residual heterogeneity in claim-level losses, reflecting unobserved variation in asset values, inventories, internal building layout, local inundation dynamics, and firm-level preparedness.

Table 9: Parsimonious address-event gross-loss models

	<i>Dependent variable: gross material loss</i>	
	OLS: log gross loss	Gamma-log: gross loss
Log unit size	0.134* (0.059)	0.193** (0.064)
Elevation	-0.208* (0.102)	-0.105 (0.102)
Registered basement	0.213 (0.369)	0.992 (0.613)
Basement unknown	0.153 (0.288)	0.219 (0.337)
Within 50 m of harbour	-0.107 (0.167)	0.139 (0.200)
Office-based	-0.017 (0.183)	-0.005 (0.185)
Industry/storage/transport	0.261 (0.204)	0.655** (0.205)
Other sector	-0.165 (0.442)	0.394 (0.418)
Event: Bodil	0.065 (0.288)	0.385 (0.278)
Event: October 2023	1.014** (0.360)	1.369** (0.405)
Constant	11.388*** (0.473)	11.073*** (0.520)
Coastal-zone fixed effects	Yes	Yes
Joint p : company groups	0.380	
Joint p : event groups	0.015	
Observations	370	370
R ²	0.159	
Adjusted R ²	0.106	
Log Likelihood		-5,313.907
Akaike Inf. Crit.		10,673.810
Residual Std. Error	1.264 (df = 347)	
F Statistic	2.986*** (df = 22; 347)	

* $p < 0.05$; ** $p < 0.01$; *** $p < 0.001$. Municipality-clustered HC1 standard errors in parentheses; p -values use a $t(G - 1)$ reference, where G is the number of municipalities.

8 Discussion

8.1 What insurance payouts identify

This paper provides a first empirical estimate of insured direct material losses for flood-affected firms using Danish administrative compensation records. The payout data from *Naturskaderådet* identify compensated direct material losses conditional on a successful claim: damage to commercial buildings, movable productive assets, inventories, equipment, and eligible clean-up costs. Mapped to the theoretical loss function in Equation (8), the outcome captures the combined insured consequence of capital damage $L_i^{(b)}$, inventory and input losses $L_i^{(c)}$, and covered building-service costs $L_i^{(bs)}$. It does not capture production interruption, delayed reopening, lost customers, supply-chain disruption, or reputational effects.

This makes the payout-based measure a lower and partial bound on the total economic burden of flooding, and the omitted components are not small. The literature reviewed in Section 2 suggests that the unobserved channels can rival or exceed insured physical damage: Mendoza-Tinoco et al. (2020) estimate indirect flood losses at 186% of direct damages across European industries, and Endendijk et al. (2024) find that each day of flood-induced interruption reduces firm revenue by roughly 0.5%. The estimates below should therefore be read as an empirical damage function for the insured physical component of storm-surge damage, while the theoretical and literature sections delineate what remains outside it. We make this distinction once here and rely on it in interpreting the results that follow.

8.2 Physical exposure, event effects, and residual heterogeneity

Insured business losses are systematically related to the physical scale of the premises and to event-level conditions. Unit size is positively associated with gross material loss in both specifications, with an elasticity of 0.13 (OLS) to 0.19 (Gamma-log) and thus below one: larger premises expose more assets, but losses rise less than proportionally with size. This is consistent with Sakai and Yao (2023), who find that smaller firms suffer disproportionately larger losses, and plausible in a business context where the marginal square metre need not contain the same density of vulnerable capital or inventory.

Elevation carries the expected negative sign. A one-metre increase is associated with roughly 19% lower loss in the OLS model (significant), but only about 10% in the Gamma-log model (not significant). This may reflect elevation explaining variation in typical claims more than in the largest claims that dominate the arithmetic mean, where unobserved factors—asset values, inventory intensity, internal layout, localized inundation—weigh more heavily. The absence of a direct flood-depth measure is a real limitation: elevation proxies exposure but cannot capture the water depth experienced at each location during a specific surge.

Event effects are the clearest finding. The October 2023 storm surge is associated with substantially higher losses than the smaller-event reference group in both specifications—approximately 176% higher in the OLS model, and a conditional mean almost four times as large (a factor of 3.9) in the Gamma-log model. Bodil is not statistically distinguishable from the reference after conditioning on covariates, and the joint test for event groups is significant ($p = 0.015$). Event-level conditions—surge extent, local water levels, duration, timing, warning and preparedness, and the composition of affected firms—therefore matter beyond building characteristics and broad coastal-zone differences.

The modest explanatory power of the OLS model ($R^2 = 0.159$, adjusted $R^2 = 0.106$) should not be read as model failure. Claim-level losses are inherently heterogeneous: two firms alike in size, elevation, sector, and coastal zone may differ greatly in the value and vulnerability of machinery, inventories, IT systems, interior installations, and preparedness, most of which is unobserved here. One caveat applies specifically to the estimated gradients rather than only to external validity. Because the address-matching procedure prioritizes precision over recall, the gradients are identified on matched claims; if match success correlates with firm type, size, or location, the size and sector coefficients could be biased and not merely less representative. The model thus captures broad, policy-relevant gradients in observed losses rather than the full claim-level damage process.

8.3 Sectoral heterogeneity and the composition of business losses

The theoretical framework predicts that storage and production firms carry both capital ($L_i^{(b)}$) and inventory ($L_i^{(c)}$) exposure and should therefore show the largest material losses (Table 1), whereas service and retail firms are more exposed through customer-facing premises and disruption channels. The data offer weak support for this specific prediction: industry, storage, and transport firms show higher mean losses descriptively, and the Gamma-log model estimates a coefficient of 0.655 for this group, implying roughly 93% higher conditional mean losses than the service/retail/hospitality reference. The direction matches both the theory and the cross-country evidence that capital-intensive and commercial entities incur the largest asset losses (Sugathan et al., 2025; Paprotny et al., 2020).

The econometric evidence is nonetheless inconclusive. The industry/storage/transport coefficient is individually significant in the Gamma-log model, but the OLS estimate is smaller and insignificant, and the joint test for company groups does not reject equality across sectors ($p = 0.380$). Because the joint test is the more conservative summary, the most defensible reading is suggestive sectoral heterogeneity—concentrated in the arithmetic mean or upper tail of losses—rather than robust differences across the whole conditional distribution. Crucially, the insurance data do not separately identify $L_i^{(b)}$ and $L_i^{(c)}$, so company group functions as a reduced-form proxy for the likely composition and

scale of exposed assets, not as a direct decomposition of capital and inventory damage. (For consistency, the company groups here correspond to the sector categories of Table 1: service/retail/hospitality to “Service and Retail,” and industry/storage/transport to “Storage and Production.”)

8.4 Implications for damage modelling and climate adaptation policy

Three implications follow. First, business losses should not be treated as scaled-up residential losses: firms differ from households in asset composition, the role of productive capital, the presence of inventories, and the economic consequences of disruption, so relevant covariates include both building and firm-type characteristics even when the outcome is restricted to insured material loss.

Second, the heterogeneity that the data robustly support is by event severity and premise scale, not by sector. Single average-payout approaches will therefore miss systematic variation along event and size dimensions, and cost-benefit analysis of flood protection should use damage functions that distinguish event contexts and business-location scale. Sector differentiation is a reasonable hypothesis—supported by theory and by descriptive patterns—but the present sample ($n = 370$) is underpowered to confirm it, so we would not yet recommend sector-specific damage parameters on the strength of these estimates alone.

Third, because the model measures insured material damage rather than total economic loss, it can inform estimates of direct compensated damage but should not stand in for the full cost of flooding. Evaluating adaptation only on insured material losses risks understating the benefits of protecting firms whose losses arise mainly through business interruption, while areas with high-value physical assets may appear disproportionately costly even where broader disruption is limited. A transparent separation of material damage from total firm loss is therefore necessary for cost-benefit analysis, local planning, and any contribution-allocation scheme.

8.5 Limitations and future research

Several limitations qualify the results. The estimation sample is restricted to positive compensated claims, so the estimates describe the intensive margin of paid claims, not expected loss among all exposed firms; firms that did not claim, fell below the deductible, or were rejected are excluded. The dependent variable is an administrative payout shaped by coverage rules, deductibles, and documentation, and so is not equivalent to the firm’s full economic loss. The precision-oriented matching reduces measurement error but yields a smaller, potentially selected sample, as noted above. The model also lacks direct measures of flood depth, duration, and indoor water level, which elevation and the spatial fixed effects only proxy. Finally, the payout data do not separate capital from inventory and movable-asset losses, so the model estimates their combined insured consequence.

Beyond addressing these limitations, several further analyses could deepen our understanding of how floods translate into firm-level losses, each targeting a component the payout data leave unobserved.

Linking losses to firm accounts. The most valuable extension would be to link claims to firms’ annual financial statements over time. Because accounting records track turnover, profit, assets, and equity year by year, a firm-level panel spanning the pre- and post-flood periods would make it possible to estimate the business-interruption and recovery components that the payout data cannot observe—the foregone profit stream over the recovery period T_R in Equation (6), and the longer-lived, persistent effects on output and performance emphasised in the theoretical framework and in the recovery literature (Section 2). This would move the analysis from the insured material loss toward the downtime and persistence channels that, for many firms, may dominate the total economic burden. As secondary benefits, linkage through firm identifiers and reporting year would allow material losses to be scaled by a firm’s asset base, and help test whether the higher losses of capital- and inventory-intensive sectors reflect fixed capital, inventories, or movable assets rather than relying on company group as a proxy.

Surveying affected firms. Much of the economic cost of flooding plausibly arises through channels administrative registers cannot capture: how long production is interrupted, how quickly a firm reopens, what costs are borne uninsured, and whether customer relationships are damaged. A survey of affected firms, compared with similar firms in unaffected areas, could recover these dimensions directly and gauge how large the business-interruption and reputational components are relative to the insured physical damage estimated here.

Learning from other production shocks. Evidence on production losses might also be drawn from settings where exogenous shutdowns are better measured. Firm-level data from the COVID-19 business compensation schemes offer estimates of the cost and duration of externally imposed stoppages across sectors and could serve as a rough benchmark for flood-induced downtime costs. The comparison is only suggestive—pandemic shutdowns and flood disruption differ in mechanism, duration, sectoral incidence, and whether premises remain usable—but such external evidence could help bound the interruption costs the present model, by design, does not observe.

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